

Bash scripts for short-read sequencing data analysis

For each sample (uMRT Rep1/Rep2 and SSII Rep1/Rep2):

1. Generate STAR Index:

```
STAR --runThreadN 8\  
--runMode genomeGenerate\  
--genomeDir /path/to/Genome/Dir\  
--genomeFastaFiles path/to/GRCh38_reference/fasta  
--sjdbGTFfile path/to/GRCh38_reference/GENCODE_45.gtf
```

2. Run STAR mapping:

```
STAR --runThreadN 8\  
--genomeDir /path/to/Genome/Dir\  
--readFilesIn /path/to/fastq.gz  
--readFilesCommand zcat\  
--outSAMtype BAM Unsorted SortedByCoordinate
```

3. Quantification with featureCounts

```
featureCounts -p --countReadPairs\  
-T 8 -t exon -g gene_id\  
-a /path/to/annotation.gtf\  
-o sample_featureCounts_output.txt\  
/path/to/aligend/BAM/Aligned.sortedByCoord.out.bam
```

4. Calculate read distribution across genomic features with RseQC

```
python3 read_distribution.py -i path/to/aligned/BAM/Aligned.sortedByCoord.out.bam\  
-r /path/to/GENCODE45/BED/File/annotation.bed
```

Code for downsampling with seqtk

```
seqtk sample -s100 /path/to/read1.fastq.gz 20000000 > subsampled_read1.fastqz  
seqtk sample -s100 /path/to/read2.fastq.gz 20000000 > subsampled_read2.fastqz
```